

Too soon for problem based learning? Learning outcomes

Ricardo Bustillo, University of the Basque Country
UPV/EHU

This paper was accepted for publication in “The International Journal of Pedagogy and Curriculum” on January 2025

ABSTRACT

In order to test whether a Problem Based Learning (PBL) intervention is less effective in the first year of a degree, a comparison between a first year subject (Introduction to Microeconomics) and a third-year one (Fiscal and Monetary Policy) has been accomplished. I examined several factors, including student participation, learning outcomes, and acquired competencies through quantitative analysis, and students’ opinions through qualitative analysis. Regarding firstly the quantitative analysis, not only overall participation but also some learning outcomes seem to reach a lower level in the first year subject. Consequently, PBL interventions seem to be more effective when they are carried out in the last phase of the degree. Second, first year students showed a much better attitude towards a PBL intervention. Therefore, despite thirdyear’s better learning outcomes, this result does not clearly suggest to prioritize PBL solely in advanced years, due to the scarce difference in results and to the fact that in the first year the challenge of the acquisition of competences is more relevant.

Keywords: Problem Based Learning, Active learning methodologies, Microeconomics, Economic Policy, Applied Economics.

JEL codes: D01, H3

1.- INTRODUCTION

Economics and Business education is currently facing significant challenges.. Today’s rapidly changing knowledge landscape can quickly render many current skills and competencies obsolete. In other words, Institutions involved in delivering tertiary education services must be held responsible for refining the work capacities of the future graduates in the so-called knowledge-based society. Skills or competences such as the ability to deal with Information and Communication Technologies, as well as to interact with other people, have recently acquired paramount relevance in the design of the syllabus of many TE subjects. Moreover, upcoming graduates will have to continue learning throughout their entire future professional career, and accordingly, higher education should prepare students for this purpose (Shin et al. 1993. Kuzu et al. 2015, Sen et al. 2022). Therefore, Tertiary Education institutions must be aware of the need to develop new approaches for the teaching learning process, aimed at facing the challenges of the knowledge-based society (Stokes, 2021).

On account of those needs, the traditional Tertiary Education knowledge transmission in the classroom (“chalk and talk lectures”) does not guarantee a proper training for future graduates. Nevertheless, traditional “Chalk and talk” lectures are still the most important part of current academic activities (Becker and Watts, 2001. Becker et al. 2006. Ray, 2018). While knowledge transfer in master classes is very important, it needs to be complemented by other different interventions in the classroom or online that aim to make the learning process more effective (Khamung et al. 2016; Bean and Melzer, 2021). However, difficulties in trying to increase student motivation can hinder better-designed interventions (Owens et al. 2020; Watts and Becker, 2008). On the other hand, active learning increases student motivation (Andrés, 2019). Therefore, it is necessary to increase student participation in the proposed interventions to avoid passive attitudes.

In this study, we utilize several vectors in order to assess the relative effectiveness of PBL applied to a subject of the first year Business and Economics Degree (Introduction to Economics: Principles of Microeconomics) with results corresponding to a subject taught in the third year of the Economics Degree (Fiscal and Monetary Policy).

Moreover, as far as we are concerned, there have not been until now studies among economics students that compare the appropriateness of the PBL approach between subjects taught in different years. Therefore, the following hypothesis shall be tested:

H1: The implementation of a PBL intervention is going to supply better results when carried out during the last years corresponding to the degree.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: in the second section, a literature review for the use of the PBL approach in Economics and Business is presented. In the third section, we reveal the general lines of the intervention. In the fourth section, we present the vectors and the comparison between both interventions, and in the fifth one, we discuss the main conclusions of this work.

2.-. LITERATURE REVIEW

Private companies as well as public institutions are already demanding graduates who must have previously acquired several skills and abilities, such as interpersonal skills or a higher capacity to adapt to new realities or to solve different problems (Quek, 2005; Tak, 2012. Chan et al. 2017. Tuononen et al. 2022). Moreover, the acquisition of adaptive expertise (Hatano and Inagaki, 1986; Anthony et al. 2015. Mylopoulos et al. 2018. Gube and Lajoie, 2020) in tertiary education has gained recently paramount relevance. The need to apply a life-learning approach to Tertiary Education has been provoked by the current higher speed of change in the background knowledge of any academic discipline. Therefore, any graduate must have acquired during the degree the ability to easily absorb new knowledge. It must be highlighted that this

phenomenon attains paramount relevance not only in the technological academic fields but also in social sciences in general. As long as the education process in the case of the PBL focus is centred in the student, since he/she must actively acquire the necessary knowledge to solve problems, this approach will make students capable of individually learning throughout their future professional career.

Moreover, the utilization of the PBL approach is coherent with the constructivist school. Piaget's (1950) constructivist focus identified the teaching-learning process not as a mere transmission of knowledge, but rather as a reconstruction process based on different learning experiences or "interventions". These latter would be carried out by instructors, who should become tutors instead of lecturers. These interventions are considered "active/cooperative learning" procedures in opposition to the traditional "passive learning" sheer knowledge transmission (Marton and Säljö, 1976. Marton and Säljö, 2014. Chen and Lin, 2020).

Although PBL was firstly applied in Medicine education in Canada (Neufeld and Barrows, 1974), we must acknowledge it as another example of types of education that are centred in the student, as the Case Study Method, developed before in Harvard Law and Business Schools (Fraser, 1931).

Most Economics and Business students face their Higher Education (HE) following a "surface approach" (Marton and Säljö, 2014) or "strategic approach" (Entwistle and Peterson, 2004. Byrne et al. 2010. Faranda et al. 2021). In other words, they are not genuinely interested in the object of study, but rather in solely obtaining a degree to find a better job. In consequence, there is, at least, a certain lack of "intrinsic motivation" in Economics subjects, a fact that helps us understand the need to design and apply attractive classroom interventions for students (Elenurm et al. 2007. Tanveer et al. 2012. Condry and Chambers, 2015. Raza et al. 2018). Problem based learning (PBL) interventions could be an alternative aimed at encouraging students to learn more deeply any of the Economics and Business subjects. PBL learning has

proved to be a strategy that favours positive student attitudes about learning (Springer et al. 1999. Andres, 2019). Moreover, PBL is related to the so-called deep approach of learning. (Marton and Säljö, 2014. Postareff et al. 2015. Dolmans et al. 2016). The main characteristic of the deep learning approach is the students' aspiration to develop a profound understanding of the topic under study. Most often, this learning activity involves a combination of conceptually related learning processes. Students who adopt a deep approach tend to be actively and interestedly involved in their studies and to participate in the individual activities of the teaching-learning process. This focus is considered an almost synonym of the attitude shown by students participating in a PBL intervention. In conclusion, PBL has proved to improve students' motivation in the teaching and learning process (Argaw et al. 2016. Sari, 2018). As an alternative strategy, some HE institutions have launched programmes to encourage and motivate first-year students to study (Kosir, 2010. Stokes, 2021; Dempsey et al. 2023).

Additionally, we should emphasize the convenience of working with examples of real companies in Business Administration degrees, highlighting that this contributes to facilitating among students the acquisition of specific and transversal skills (Lobo et al. 2009. Jiménez et al. 2013. Van Aken and Berends. 2018). Unlike previous studies because they use qualitative research, Marín et al. (2009), after examining the results of a survey among recently graduate economists, conclude that those University Colleges that apply the PBL approach are the best valued. An alternative piece of recent research has confirmed the acceptance by students of a structured application of the PBL approach, amongst business undergraduate studies (Silva et al. 2028).

Regarding the academic literature on the effectiveness of the PBL approach among Economics and Business students, most studies tend to support PBL interventions because of their higher learning outcomes (Strobel and Van Barneveld, 2009. Maros et al. 2023; Mergendoller et al. 2006; Suryawati et al. 2020. Mujumdar et al. 2021). However, a strand of work has shown not only difficulties of application, but also certain lack of evidence in reference to its alleged

positive effect on students' learning outcomes. For instance, some studies have shown cultural difficulties when applying the PBL approach in non-Western countries, a fact that makes its utilization less effective in comparison with the outcome in Western countries, where these interventions were created and firstly applied (Chan et al. 2024). These studies suggest the application of flexible approaches of the PBL procedure, for instance giving more importance to the instructor's role in countries where an authority figure is a key element of the education system (Chan et al. 2024).

For instance, Maxwell et al. (2005) state that PBL can just slightly improve learning outcomes (among high school students) in comparison with traditional classes only when implemented by well trained instructors in both the PBL procedures and economics. Additionally, Fassbender et al. (2022) revealed that a PBL application "did not show any increase in students' knowledge of economics". However, the qualitative analysis associated to this research shows a positive sway not only on the learning environment but also on students' attitude, therefore improving their competences.

Finally yet importantly, De Witte and Rogge (2016) show in a randomized experiment that, students in a PBL course do not obtain higher results than those in a traditionally taught course. Among articles revealing obstacles to implement PBL, Gorbaneff (2010) highlights the lack of material that can be utilized or the particular nature of Business science. Rigalt-i-Torrent (2011) also warn about the lack of suitable materials to develop PBL approach properly.

Because of the review of the above mentioned literature, we can conclude that we still need to continue measuring the effectiveness of the PBL approach.

3. METHODOLOGY

The academic literature has highlighted two differential contributions in reference to the PBL-based interventions. In the first place, since it is a student-centred teaching-learning process, it

tends to favour intrinsic motivation in carrying out the assigned tasks. This also results in an improvement in learning outcomes (Siminica and Dumitru, 2013. Condry and Chambers, 2015; Raza et al. 2018). The second contribution to be mentioned is the one linked to the acquisition of transversal competences, such as teamwork, skills in the management of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) or oral and written expression (Forsythe, 2010).

With regard to subjects in the field of Economics and Business in particular, the use of the PBL would reinforce the acquisition of specific competences. Choosing specific case studies (countries or productive sectors) thus using actual data improves the motivation of the students, because the assigned tasks are aimed at solving a “driving question” or ratifying a hypothesis related to a current economic issue. The resolution of the tasks will entail an effort to search for different sources of information. Subsequently, the students must base the reasoning on the previously acquired knowledge, as a result of their own learning effort, but always with the help and support of the teacher.

These classroom interventions have been designed with the purpose of introducing the students in easily understandable economic questions, directly related to issues faced either in real life or in the everyday management of firms or other institutions. Specifically, in the introductory course Introduction to economics, principles of microeconomics, students were proposed to calculate the elasticity of demand in different markets (housing, automobile) in order to assess the effectiveness of different policies, such as price controls or tax burdens. In particular, students must examine how elasticities affect the tax burden or other intervention in competitive markets, once they have gathered statistical information to estimate a demand function of the market.

The thirdyear subject (Fiscal and Monetary Policy), which belongs to the macroeconomics field of knowledge, examines the issue regarding how governments’ counter-cyclical budget policies must face the objective of short run stabilization. That is to say, fiscal policy must reduce the

output gap by bringing effective production closer to the level of potential production. With this objective, students must carry out the estimation of the fiscal multiplier, in addition to acquiring skills in the areas of obtaining data from official sources and its subsequent processing in a spreadsheet. In this subject, students must conclude whether the exercise of a counter-cyclical fiscal policy in different European countries is compatible with compliance with the Stability Pact in the medium run, especially amongst countries of the Eurozone.

The two tasks are complemented by a presentation of the results by the different groups participating in the intervention. The presentation of results and their subsequent discussion is carried out through an online platform, so that the students can become familiar with this kind of computer software, thus influencing the acquisition of transversal skills. Specifically, the software used in order to make the online presentations was “Blackboard Collaborate”.

4.- CONCEPTUAL MODEL Regarding the conceptual model that has been developed in this article, as mentioned in the introduction, the objective of this piece of research is to compare the learning outcomes obtained by the application of a PBL intervention in different years. In consequence, we calculate whether the difference between the average grades obtained in First and Third year is negative and statistically significant, as it had been previously put forward.

$$FG_{1stYear} - FG_{3rdYear} = Difference \quad (i)$$

As hypothesized before, we expect a negative and statistically significant value for the difference between $FG_{1stYear}$ and $FG_{3rdYear}$, where “FG” stands for final grade. Additionally, I consider not only the learning outcomes registered throughout the application of the intervention, but also the assessment of the students, as shown in Table 1

Table 1. Variables taken into consideration in the Conceptual Model

Variable	First Year	Third Year	Difference	Expected Sign
Final Grade	FG1	FG3	FG1- FG3	Negative
PBL Task Grade, Final Exam	PBLG1	PBLG3	PBLG1- PBLG3	Negative
PBL Multiple Choice Grade	MCG1	MCG3	MCG1- MCG3	Negative
PBL Assessment	PBLA1	PBLA3	PBLA1- PBLA3	Negative

Source: Author's elaboration.

5- RESULTS

In order to carry out the comparison we have taken into account different vectors; in particular, we have taken into consideration firstly the final exam's average mark corresponding to the particular exercise whose knowledge was developed in the PBL intervention (PBL Task Grade, Final Exam). Additionally, the total final exam average grade has also been compared (Final Grade).

Table 2. FIRST YEAR: Descriptive statistics of the intervention

	<i>PBL Students</i>				<i>No PBL Students</i>	
	Final Grade	PBL Task Grade, Final Exam	PBL Mult. Choice Grade	PBL Assessment	Final Grade	PBL Task Grade, Final Exam
Mean	4.8565	3.4108	4.7895	8.2125	5.4175	3.0625
Median	4.725	2.4	5	8	5	2.9
Minimum	0.2	0	0	7	1.5	0
Maximum	9.45	10	10	9.7	9.1	8
Standard deviation	2.5332	3.1822	3.1551	1.1196	2.0591	2.6288
Coefficient of Variation	0.50801	0.93298	0.65875	0.13633	0.39693	0.85838
Skewness	-0.022	0.68243	-0.075894	0.19832	0.00303	0.44824
Ex. Kurtosis	-0.7588	-0.87469	-0.98799	-1.6154	-0.46197	-1.0442
Sample Size	39	66.10%			20	32.90%

Source: Author's elaboration.

Secondly, we have registered as second vector the average grade obtained in a multiple-choice (PBL, Multiple Choice Grade) exercise answered in the last day when the intervention took place, which measures the knowledge acquisition due to the intervention. Thirdly, we have included the percentage of students taking part in the PBL intervention, as they had the option of doing it or not depending on which assessment system they opted to. The general legislation of the University allows the students to choose between a continuous assessment system or, alternatively, sitting a final exam, which would provide 100% of the grade for the subject. In other words, students have the right to be assessed in a unique final examination in case they opt for that choice. The mark granted for participating in the PBL exercise was similar in the two compared subjects, in particular it reached 10% of the whole grade of the subject. However, we have also considered the grade obtained by students not participating in the PBL, in order to assess whether the latter obtained lower marks or not, thus confirming the suitability of this classroom intervention.

Finally, in order to measure the opinion of the students they completed a survey where they had to reveal with a Likert (1932) scale from 1 to 10 their opinion about the intervention. Moreover, students carried out additionally a qualitative assessment of the overall development and appropriateness of each PBL intervention (PBL Assessment).

Table 3. THIRD YEAR: Descriptive statistics of the intervention

	<i>PBL Students</i>				<i>No PBL Students</i>	
	Final Grade	PBL Task Grade, Final Exam	PBL Mult. Choice Grade	PBL Assessment	Final Grade	PBL Task Grade, Final Exam
Mean	5.4093	5.7915	7.9222	7.4483	5.45	2.36
Median	5.3175	5.7915	8	7.5	5.45	2.18
Minimum	0	0.7	0	5	1.5	0.7
Maximum	9.926	10	10	9	9.25	5
Standard deviation	2.4142	3.2928	1.5985	0.8443	2.4668	1.4759
Coefficient of Variation	0.44221	0.56855	0.20177	0.11336	0.45262	0.6254
Skewness	-0.1438	-0.20054	-2.5018	-0.70287	-0.0071794	0.8813
Ex. Kurtosis	-0.2607	-1.4613	11.268	0.99264	-0.90848	-0.11479
Sample Size	59	73.70%			21	26.30%

Source: Author's elaboration.

Tables 1 and 2 show the main descriptive statistics that will be analyzed later in more detail.

The first figure to be compared between the first and third years is the percentage of participation in the PBL intervention. In the first year, both the grades and the percentage of participation in the PBL intervention are lower compared to the third grade. This outcome is not really surprising given the usually heterogeneous composition of students in first years Economics and Business degrees.

Moreover, the standard deviation of the scores does not show relevant differences between the different categories collected in the two tables.

The comparison of grades between the students who followed the PBL intervention and those who did not shows that the final grade hardly varies between the two collected groups. PBL students only register a higher grade in the final exam task studied with the PBL intervention.

This difference is more evident if we only take into account the results registered among third-year students.

Fig. 1. 1st Three Vectors: Year 1 vs. Year 3

In Figure 1 we can also observe that third year students obtained in general higher grades. Despite the fact that the difference in the mark corresponding to the whole final exam is almost negligible (lower than half point), however the mark corresponding to the matter specifically developed during the PBL exercise was more than two points higher in the thirdyear subject. This result tends to confirm for the moment the hypothesis put forward in the introduction.

In order to test the statistical significance of the divergences in the grades between first and third year students, a contrast of differences between means was carried out for the three marks described above, as well as for the assessment provided by the students to the PBL intervention. (Table 4).

Table 4. First and Third Year PBL students. Contrast of differences between means

Variable	Mean difference (1°-3°)	t	t Critical Value, 95%	Degrees of Freedom
Final Grade	-0.56230	-0.90667	1.98552	94
PBL Task Grade, Final Exam	-2.38069	-2.63830	2.00404	55
PBL Multiple Choice Grade	-2.19230	-5.82132	1.98969	81
PBL Assessment	0.76422	3.60710	1.98729	88

Source: Author's elaboration.

With the exception of the final grade, the one to which we should grant a lower degree of relevance in this analysis, the other two variables (the grade of the PBL task inside the final exam and the exam within the PBL) show a statistically significant difference in favour of third year students, as it is shown in Table 4. Consequently, the initial hypothesis put forward in the introduction of the article is confirmed by this result.

On the contrary, there is no statistically significant difference between the final exam scores between first and third years.

Lastly, there is also a statistically significant difference, in this case in favour of first-year students, with regard to the assessment of the PBL intervention. This outcome underlines the fact that first-year students seemed to be more enthusiastic than third-year ones to this classroom intervention.

Fig. 2: First year: Marks in Exams, PBL vs. no PBL

Regarding the comparison between PBL and no PBL students (Figure 2), we can see that in first year, although “no PBL” students obtain a higher average mark in the entire exam (5.42 vs. 4.85), “no PBL” students obtained a lower mark in the part related to the matter developed by the PBL intervention. However, the difference is not statistically significant either (Table 5), therefore, the effect of the PBL intervention on the final score could be considered almost insignificant (only 0.35 higher).

Table 5. PBL - no PBL. First and Third Year. Contrast of differences between means

	Mean difference (PBL- no PBL)	t	t Critical Value, 95%	Degrees of Freedom
FIRST YEAR				
Final Grade	-0.57000	-0.27652	2.00758	51
PBL Task Grade, Final Exam	0.34831	0.38420	2.00758	51
THIRD YEAR				
Final Grade	-0.04	-0.0116075	1.99546893	68
PBL Task Grade, Final Exam	3.4315	2.18102712	2.06865761	23

Source: Author’s elaboration.

Fig. 3: Third year: Marks in Exams, PBL vs. no PBL

In third year (Figure 3) the mark in the entire final exam is also similar, and we additionally observe the same difference in the mark of the PBL matter exercise, a fact that confirms again that PBL intervention allowed a deeper understanding of that part of the matter. The difference in grades in this case is statistically significant (Table 5).

In contrast with the first year result, PBL students obtained an average mark three points higher than no PBL ones, what confirms in his case the effectiveness of the intervention, as well as unveils again that its effect is stronger among Third year students. The initial hypothesis seems again to be confirmed by these results.

Fig. 4: Participation and Students Assessment

Finally, participation in PBL (Figure 4) was higher in third year (74% participation against 66% participation). Nevertheless, when measuring the students' opinion, first year students rated the PBL intervention with a higher mark (8.2) than third year ones (7.45). In the qualitative assessment provided by the students, first year ones seemed to show a much more positive perception of the intervention, with expressions such as "a beautiful way to learn elasticity" or "a useful project in order to understand the subject".

On the contrary, in third year many students showed their reluctance to this kind of classroom intervention. In particular, they expressed that "it has been difficult for them to collect the data from data bases", despite the fact that we had used a computer room lecture to solve a preliminary exercise.

Students also expressed that they would have preferred a written multiple-choice exam instead, so that they could have the opportunity to have studied previously that part of the matter before the final exam's date. We can understand this attitude once considered that students show a more and more "strategic" approach (Entwistle and Peterson, 2004. Marton and Säljö, 2014; Faranda et al. 2021) to learning when they see themselves close to the end of the degree. In consequence, from that point of view PBL must be considered more interesting to be applied

in the moment when students show the best attitude to active/collaborative classroom interventions, otherwise the potential positive effects of these actions could be hindered.

Instructors must nuance the obtained quantitative results, especially when considering that in first year the number of transversal competences to develop is higher. Moreover, there is always a bias when comparing marks corresponding to different years, since in the first one results are almost inevitably poorer than among higher years' students, partly because towards the end of the degree there is a lower enrolment after many have abandoned the studies. This is particularly relevant in the Spanish University, where the dropout rate of University students is quite high, as many give up their studies once having finished the first year.

6.- DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, I expose the reasons put forward in the recent academic literature that justify the application of active methodologies in the University. In particular, two basic advantages linked to active learning have been highlighted: the increase in students' intrinsic motivation and their greater capacity in order to favour the acquisition of not only specific and transversal competencies, but also adaptive expertise. In this way, students would be prepared in a more suitable manner to face the future challenge of lifelong learning.

The PBL methodology has been applied in two subjects taught in the first and third years of the degree in economics. The results obtained in both are compared to try to confirm whether PBL interventions are more effective in the case of subjects taught in the last years of the degree.

For this purpose, the total grades and in particular the learning outcomes corresponding to the specific matter covered by the ABP intervention have been used as elements of analysis.

In reference to the quantitative results, the assessment of certain learning outcomes tends to confirm the hypothesis put forward in the beginning of the article, that is to say, that PBL interventions seem to be more effective when they are carried out in the last phase of the degree.

We must acknowledge that the acquisition of knowledge corresponding to first year students is still reduced compared to third year ones, a fact that must be taken into consideration because it biases the results. Consequently, the learning outcomes will tend to be clearly worse. The results suggest that whereas PBL application can be positive, its implementation might need to be adapted based on the students' level of study. For first-year students, a scaffolded approach to PBL might be necessary, gradually increasing complexity as they progress through their degree, thus following Vygotsky's (1986) zone of proximal development approach. Consequently, these differences should not allow us to prioritize the use of problem-based learning only in advanced courses, due to the scarce difference in results and to the fact that in the first year the challenge of the acquisition of competences is more relevant. Moreover, we should also take into consideration that a number of students in first year will later give up the studies before reaching to the third year, as shown by the high dropout rate of the Spanish University students. Therefore, we must nuance the results obtained from the quantitative analysis and thus we must be cautious when suggesting recommendations. The positive attitude shown by first year students to these interventions should also be taken into consideration, since a good attitude granted by students is needed for the success of any of these active/cooperative procedures. The negative attitude shown by third year students can be better understood if we consider that they mostly follow a strategical approach to learning, hence showing a lack of intrinsic motivation, at least to a certain degree

The findings suggest that a strict application of PBL might be more effective in later years of study, which has practical implications for curriculum design. Active learning interventions such as relatively complex PBL approaches ought to be located in the last years of study, when this kind of active teaching can be more beneficial for students. Moreover, current University students must be trained for life-long learning throughout their future professional career, and therefore PBL must be considered in curriculum design (amongst the suggested activities of subjects), not only in the last years of the degrees, but also in the first ones in a scaffolded way.

The positive results in both interventions (the most intense acquisition of specific and transversal competences) suggest the extension of this type of learning approaches to other subjects.

Besides, although this research has been carried out based on a small sample of students, future studies ought to utilize this methodology for larger samples and outcomes corresponding to several academic years. Although the object of research is limited to Business and Economic Degrees in Spain, PBL should also be utilized in other different educational contexts beyond the economics discipline. Additionally, I recommend the extension of PBL to other geographical areas outside the European University.

In line with this last statement, the limited scope of this study suggests that further research and discussion on the application of these interventions are still needed to reach a better understanding of the benefits of the PBL approach.

REFERENCES

- Andres, H. P. (2019). Active teaching to manage course difficulty and learning motivation. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 43(2), 220-235.
- Anthony, G., Hunter, J., & Hunter, R. (2015). "Prospective teachers development of adaptive expertise". *Teaching and teacher education*, 49, 108-117.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0742051X15000608>
- Argaw, A. S., Haile, B. B., Ayalew, B. T., & Kuma, S. G. (2016). The effect of problem based learning (PBL) instruction on students' motivation and problem solving skills of physics. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 13(3), 857-871.
- Bean, J. C., & Melzer, D. (2021). *Engaging ideas: The professor's guide to integrating writing, critical thinking, and active learning in the classroom*. John Wiley & Sons.

Becker, William E; Watts, Michael; Becker, Suzanne R., eds. (2006): Teaching Economics: More Alternatives to Chalk and Talk. Cheltenham, U.K. and Northampton, Mass.: Elgar. p xiv, 225.

Becker William E. & Michael Watts (2001) "Teaching Economics at the Start of the 21st Century: Still Chalk-and-Talk." *American Economic Review*, vol. 91(2), pages 446-451, May. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1257/aer.91.2.446>

Byrne, M., Finlayson, O., Flood, B., Lyons, O., & Willis, P. (2010). "A comparison of the learning approaches of accounting and science students at an Irish university". *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 34(3), 369-383. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0309877X.2010.484055>

Chan, C. K., Fong, E. T., Luk, L. Y., & Ho, R. (2017). "A review of literature on challenges in the development and implementation of generic competencies in higher education curriculum". *International Journal of Educational Development*, 57, 1-10.

Chan, S. C. C., Gondhalekar, A. R., Choa, G., & Rashid, M. A. (2024). Adoption of problem-based learning in medical schools in non-western countries: a systematic review. *Teaching and learning in medicine*, 36(2), 111-122.

Chen, J., & Lin, T. F. (2020). "Do cooperative-based learning groups help students learn microeconomics?" *SAGE Open*, 10(3), pp 1-7. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244020938699>

Condry, J., & Chambers, J. (2015). Intrinsic motivation and the process of learning. In *The hidden costs of reward* (pp. 61-84). Psychology Press.

De Witte, K., & Rogge, N. (2016). "Problem-based learning in secondary education: evaluation by an experiment". *Education Economics*, 24(1), 58-82. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09645292.2014.966061>

- Dempsey, A. M., Nolan, Y. M., Lone, M., & Hunt, E. (2023). Examining Motivation of First-Year Undergraduate Anatomy Students Through the Lens of Universal Design for Learning (UDL): A Single Institution Study. *Medical Science Educator*, 33(4), 945-953.
- Dolmans, D. H., Loyens, S. M., Marcq, H., & Gijbels, D. (2016). Deep and surface learning in problem-based learning: a review of the literature. *Advances in health sciences education*, 21, 1087-1112.
- Elenurm, T., Ennulo, J., & Laar, J. (2007). "Structures of motivation and entrepreneurial orientation in students as the basis for differentiated approaches in developing human resources for future business initiatives". *EBS Review*, vol. 23, pp. 50-61.
- Entwistle, N. J., & Peterson, E. R. (2004). "Conceptions of learning and knowledge in higher education: Relationships with study behaviour and influences of learning environments". *International Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 41, 407-428.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2005.08.009>
- Faranda, W. T., Clarke, T. B., & Clarke III, I. (2021). Marketing student perceptions of academic program quality and relationships to surface, deep, and strategic learning approaches. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 43(1), 9-24.
- Fassbender, U., Papenbrock, J., & Pilz, M. (2022). Teaching entrepreneurship to life-science students through Problem Based Learning. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20(3), 100685.
- Forsythe, F. (2010) "Problem-based learning." In *The handbook for economics lecturers*.
<https://www.economicsnetwork.ac.uk/advice/pbl>
- Fraser, C. E. (1931). *The case method of instruction*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Gorbanev, I. (2010). "Qué se Puede Aprender de la Literatura Sobre el Aprendizaje Basado en Problemas" (What Can Be Learned from Literature About Learning Based in Problems?).

Revista Facultad de Ciencias Económicas: Investigación y Reflexión, 18(1), 61-74.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.18359/rfce.2001>

Gube, M., & Lajoie, S. (2020). “Adaptive expertise and creative thinking: A synthetic review and implications for practice”. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 35, 100630.

Hatano, G., and Inagaki, K. (1986). “Two Courses of Expertise,” in *Child Development and Education in Japan*, H. Stevenson, H. Azuma, and K. Hakuta eds., Freeman, New York, pp. 262–272.

Jareño, Francisco, (2011). “Experiencia docente en la Facultad de CC. Económicas y Empresariales de Albacete”, in Farinós, J. E. y Soriano, P. (coord.), *Innovación Educativa en Finanzas en la implantación del Espacio Europeo de Educación Superior*. Valencia, Spain: Reproexpres Ediciones, Pp. 1-20.

Jiménez, J. J., Lagos, G., & Jareño, F. (2013). “El Aprendizaje Basado en Problemas como instrumento potenciador de las competencias transversales”. *E-pública, Revista electrónica sobre la enseñanza de la Economía Pública* nº 13, pp. 44, 68. <https://e-publica.unizar.es/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/133JIMENEZVF.pdf>

Jones, B. D. , Epler, C. M. , Mokri, P. , Bryant, L. H. , & Parette, M. C. (2013). “The Effects of a Collaborative Problem-based Learning Experience on Students’ Motivation in Engineering Capstone Courses.” *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 7(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7771/1541-5015.1344>

Khamung, R., Majumdar, B., & Pongruengphant, R. (2016). Active Learning for Knowledge Development and Management: A Case Study at Bangsaen, Thailand. *The International Journal of Learning in Higher Education*, 24(1), 1.

- Kosir, S. (2010). "Study support as students' motivation for study". *International Journal of Management in education*, 4(1), 25-45.
<https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJMIE.2010.02988>
- Kuzu, S., Demir, S., & Canpolat, M. (2015). Evaluation of life-long learning tendencies of pre-service teachers in terms of some variables. *Eğitimde Kuram ve Uygulama*.
- Likert, R. (1932). "A technique for the measurement of attitudes". *Archives of psychology*, 140: 1-55.
- Lobo Gallardo, A., Escobar Pérez, B., & Arquero Montaña, J. L. (2009). "Using empirical based case studies to improve motivation, non-technical skills and content learning: a longitudinal study of an EHEA experience". *Innovar*, 19; pp. 43-52.
<http://www.fce.unal.edu.co/media/files/innovar/EDUCACION2009.pdf>
- Marín, Salvador, Antón, Marcos and Mercedes Palacios (2009). "An empirical study of economists and the new graduate and postgraduate economics' degrees", *Innovar*, 19; pp. 111- 129. <http://www.fce.unal.edu.co/media/files/innovar/EDUCACION2009.pdf>
- Maros, M., Korenkova, M., Fila, M., Levicky, M., & Schoberova, M. (2023). Project-based learning and its effectiveness: evidence from Slovakia. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(7), 4147-4155. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10494820.2021.1954036>
- Marton, F., & Säljö, R. (1976). "On qualitative differences in learning, II—outcome as a function of the learner's conception of the task". *The British Journal of Educational Psychology*, Vol. 46(1), 115–127. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8279.1976.tb02304.x>
- Marton, F., & Säljö, R. (2014). Approaches to learning. In F. Marton, D. Hounsell, & N. Entwistle (Eds.), *The experience of learning: Implications for teaching and studying in higher education* (3rd [Internet] ed., pp. 106-125). University of Edinburgh, Centre for Teaching, Learning, and Assessment.

- Maxwell, N. L., Mergendoller, J. R., & Bellisimo, Y. (2005). "Problem-based learning and high school macroeconomics: A comparative study of instructional methods". *The Journal of Economic Education*, 36(4), 315-329. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3200/JECE.36.4.315-331>
- Mergendoller, J. R., Maxwell, N. L., & Bellisimo, Y. (2006). The effectiveness of problem-based instruction: A comparative study of instructional methods and student characteristics. *Interdisciplinary journal of problem-based learning*, 1(2), 49-69. <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/ijpbl/article/view/28108>
- Mylopoulos, M., Kulasegaram, K., & Woods, N. N. (2018). "Developing the experts we need: fostering adaptive expertise through education". *Journal of evaluation in clinical practice*, 24(3), 674-677.
- Neufeld, V. R., & Barrows, H. S. (1974). The "McMaster Philosophy": an approach to medical education. *Academic Medicine*, 49(11), 1040-50.
- Owens, D. C., Sadler, T. D., Barlow, A. T., & Smith-Walters, C. (2020). Student motivation from and resistance to active learning rooted in essential science practices. *Research in Science Education*, 50, 253-277.
- Piaget, Jean. (1950). *The Psychology of Intelligence*. New York: Routledge.
- Postareff, L., Parpala, A., & Lindblom-Ylänne, S. (2015). Factors contributing to changes in a deep approach to learning in different learning environments. *Learning Environments Research*, 18, 315-333.
- Quek, A. (2005), "Learning for the workplace: a case study in graduate employees' generic competencies", *Journal of Workplace Learning*, Vol. 17 No. 4, pp. 231-242. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13665620510597185>

- Ray, M. (2018). "Teaching economics using 'cases'—Going beyond the 'chalk-and-talk' method". *International Review of Economics Education*, 27, 1-9.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1477388017300531>
- Raza, S. A., Qazi, W., & Shah, N. (2018). "Factors affecting the motivation and intention to become an entrepreneur among business university students". *International Journal of Knowledge and Learning*, 12(3), 221-241.
<https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJKL.2018.092315>
- Rigall-i-Torrent, R. (2011). "Using problem-based learning for introducing producer theory and market structure", *International Review of Economics Education*, 10(1), 1-15.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1477-3880\(15\)30043-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1477-3880(15)30043-8)
- Sari, I. K. (2018). The effect of problem-based learning and project-based learning on the achievement motivation. *Jurnal Prima Edukasia*, 6(2), 129-135.
- Şen, N., & Yildiz Durak, H. (2022). Examining the relationships between English teachers' lifelong learning tendencies with professional competencies and technology integrating self-efficacy. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(5), 5953-5988.
- Shin, J. H., Haynes, R. B., & Johnston, M. E. (1993). "Effect of problem-based, self-directed undergraduate education on life-long learning". *CMAJ: Canadian Medical Association Journal*, 148(6), 969. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1490700/>
- Silva, A. B. D., Bispo, A. C. K. D. A., Rodriguez, D. G., & Vasquez, F. I. F. (2018). Problem-based learning: A proposal for structuring PBL and its implications for learning among students in an undergraduate management degree program. *Revista de Gestão*, 25(2), 160-177.

- Siminica, M. and Dumitru, A. (2013). "Self-directed learning in economic education". *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(12).
<https://www.ijern.com/journal/December-2013/23.pdf>
- Springer, L., Stanne, M. E., and Donovan, S. S. (1999) "Measuring the Success of Small-Group Learning on Undergraduates in Science, Mathematics, Engineering and Technology: A Meta-Analysis." *Review of Educational Research*, 69, 21–51.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.3102/00346543069001021>
- Stokes, J. (2021). "Those Skills to Take on the World": Developing Capitals through University Enabling Programs. *International Journal of Learning in Higher Education*, 28(2).
- Strobel, J., & Van Barneveld, A. (2009). When is PBL more effective? A meta-synthesis of meta-analyses comparing PBL to conventional classrooms. *Interdisciplinary journal of problem-based learning*, 3(1), 44-58.
<https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/ijpbl/article/view/28220>
- Suryawati, E., Suzanti, F., Zulfarina, Z., Putriana, A. R., & Febrianti, L. (2020). The implementation of local environmental problem-based learning student worksheets to strengthen environmental literacy. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 9(2), 169-178.
- Tak, J. (2012). "Career adapt-abilities scale—Korea form: Psychometric properties and construct validity". *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 80(3), 712-715.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0001879112000103>
- Tanveer, M. A., Shabbir, M. F., Ammar, M., Dolla, S. I., & Aslam, H. D. (2012). "Influence of teacher on student' learning motivation in management sciences studies". *American Journal of Scientific Research*, 67(1), 76-87.
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Muhammad-Tanveer-27/publication/320016551_Influence_of_Teacher_on_Student'_Learning_Motivation_in

[Management Sciences Studies/links/59c8ee22a6fdccc71929c98a/Influence-of-Teacher-on-Student-Learning-Motivation-in-Management-Sciences-Studies.pdf](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359822222/links/59c8ee22a6fdccc71929c98a/Influence-of-Teacher-on-Student-Learning-Motivation-in-Management-Sciences-Studies.pdf)

- Tuononen, T., Hyytinen, H., Kleemola, K., Hailikari, T., Männikkö, I., & Toom, A. (2022). “Systematic Review of Learning Generic Skills in Higher Education—Enhancing and Impeding Factors”. In *Frontiers in education* (Vol. 7, p. 885917).
- Van Aken, J. E., & Berends, H. (2018). Problem solving in organizations. Cambridge university press.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1986). Thought and language. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Watts, Michael and William E. Becker (2008) “A Little More than Chalk and Talk: Results from a Third National Survey of Teaching Methods in Undergraduate Economics Courses”. *The Journal of Economic Education*. Vol. 39, Number, pp. 273 – 286.